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NUTRITIONAL AND MEDICINAL IMPORTANCE OF DATES IN THE LIGHT OF QURAN, HADITH, AND MEDICAL SCIENCE

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NUTRITIONAL AND MEDICINAL IMPORTANCE OF DATES IN THE LIGHT OF QURAN, HADITH, AND MEDICAL SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The date palm is a historic plant in the history of Islam that has been grown for ages in the Arab deserts for its consumable fruit. Fruits contain a lot of calories, dietary fiber, and several vital vitamins and minerals. Palm fruits are abundant in minerals, lipids, and protein and are a great source of dietary fiber. In this research paper, we will examine how dates are utilized in ancient medical practices to treat a variety of maladies in addition to their nutritional worth. According to a phytochemical study, Fruits contain substances with various health benefits, including anthocyanins, phenols, sterols, carotenoids, procyanidins, and flavonoids. Studies in medicine have revealed results that palm fruits have no radical scavenging, antioxidant, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, anti-cancer, and immunostimulant properties are present in palm fruits. The pharmacological characteristics of palm fruits and seeds and their significance in the Quran, Hadith, and Islamic literature are confirmed by this study's thorough research of phytochemistry.

According to temperament, experimental curative results are improved. Advance medicinal results are shown in which temperament palm fruit is curative and when it has side effects study case is improved in the view of Islamic literature Quran Hadith and medical science.

Keywords: Quran, hadith, Date, Nutritional, Medicinal.

Introduction

Date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) has long been one of the most important fruit crops in the arid regions of the Arabian Peninsula, North Africa, and the Middle East Over the past three centuries, dates have been introduced into new production areas in Australia, India/Pakistan, Mexico, South Africa, South America, and the United States. Dates are an important source of income and staple food for local populations in many of the countries where they are grown, it has played an important role in the economy, society, and environment of those countries

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Dates are one of the oldest fruit crops and have been cultivated for at least 5000 years in North Africa and the Middle East.¹ The earliest records from Iraq (Mesopotamia) show that the dating culture was probably established around 3000 BC. Due to the long history of date culture and the wide distribution and exchange of date palm crops, the origin of the date palm is unknown, but it probably originated in the ancient Mesopotamia region (southern Iraq) or western India (Wrigley, 1995).² From its original center, date palm cultivation spread to the Arabian Peninsula, North Africa, and the Middle East. The culture of history spread to Egypt by the middle of the second century BCE. The spread of date palm cultivation later spread to southern Spain and Pakistan along with the spread of Islam. The Spaniards were the first to introduce dates outside the Arabian Peninsula, North Africa, and the Middle East/South Asia, taking them to the Americas.³ Now palm trees are being cultivated in different provinces of Pakistan.

Methodology

In this research work, we will collect data from the Quran, Hadith, Medical books, other research papers, and literature on botanical classification and medicinal properties collected from the internet in this research paper we will adopt qualitative and quantitative with the standard research approach in this study I have mentioned my experiments with temperamental situation on different patients.

Literature Review

Dates are a significant source of food in many cultures and they hold both nutritional and medicinal importance in Islam they hold a special place they are mentioned in the Quran and Hadith with their various benefits Additionally medical science has recognized their Dates are a significant source of food in many cultures and they hold both nutritional and medicinal importance in Islam they hold a special place nutritional and medicinal properties.

From the historical study of dates, it is clear that it is mentioned frequently in ancient books, but it has also been described many times in the Quran and Hadith. Dates have been mentioned in the Holy Quran in twenty (22) places. In the books of hadith, chapters have been made on it, dates have been described briefly, and the methidathion has also mentioned their own opinions on it. Dates are also mentioned in medical books written from ancient times to modern times.

Dates are mentioned in the Holy Qur'an, Hadith books in Sahih Bukhari, Imam Bukhari Muhammad bin Ismail, Imam Muslim bin Hajjaj in Sahih Muslim, Muhammad bin Yazid in Sunan Ibn Majah, Sunan Abi Dawud Sulaiman bin Ishaat Sajastani in his books. In the medical books, Imam Zahahbi mentioned Prophetic Medicine, Raghib Asfhani mentioned in Prophetic Medicine, Ibn Qayyim mentioned Prophetic Medicine. Al-Hawi in medicine: Abu Bakr, Muhammad bin Zakaria Al-Razi (d. 313 AH),⁴ and Dr. Khalid Gaznavi mentioned Prophetic Medicine and Modern Science.

Here the question arises in the mind that when it has been mentioned since ancient times, it has been described by different people in their books, so what is the need to write more about it now when it is mentioned in the Quran and Hadith books? And *Muhadditheen* has also taken it as a topic in their books. So, the answer is that research has created a

revolution in modern times, research has given birth to new ways that have surprised the world. has given So far, *Muhadditheen* and researchers have described it as a food and most of the researchers have improved it that its temperament is hotter, while there is still a need for research on the medical components found in it, meditational value, meditational properties. The nature of its research initiatives has also changed, qualitative research has been done on it, but quantitative research on the gradients found in it is an important need of time.

Discussion

Phoenix dactylifera L.

English Name	Date
Local Name	Khajoor
Arabic Name	Tamar
Kingdom	Plantae
Sub kingdom	Trecheobionta
Super division	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Liliopsid
Subclass	Arescidae
Order	Aric ales
Family	Arecaceae
Genus	Phoenix L
Species	phoenix dactylifera L
Scientific Name	<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>
Habit and Habit	cultivated tree and may be found self-grown
Distribution	Middle East South Asia and North Africa
Part used	fruit
Meditational use	used in heart and skin diseases antidote kidney's swelling and intestinal Pain, heart attack, wound, healer diarrhea, labor pain, sexual weakness, stomach pain, and piles

Quranic name; Nikhil, Nakheel, Nakhleh. (نخل، نخيل، نخلة) Apart from this, its other names are as follows.

	French	Datte	English	Date
	Italian	Dattero	Latin	Palmilla
	Greek	Foiniks	Hebrew	Tamaris
	Russian	Feenik	Spanish	Datil
	Arabic	Nakhal	Persian	Tumir
	Sanskrit	Kharchour	Persian. Urdu. Punjabi	Kharma

Al-Nahl is an Arabic word. And in the Holy Qur'an, Nakhl نخل Nakheel نخيل Nakhla نخله has been mentioned. Is an Arabic word and in the Holy Quran, Nakhl Nakheel Nakhla has been mentioned

"نَخْلٌ ٢ [جمع]: جج نخيل، مف نخلة: (نت) جنس شجر من فصيلة النخليات أنواعه عديدة، تعيش جميعها في المناطق الحارة، ساقه رفيعة مستقيمة طويلة ذات عقد، أوراقه سعفية ريشية الشكل. يزرع للزينة أو لثماره مستطيلة الشكل لذينة الطعم التي تعدّ من أفضل التمار المغذية وهي التمر."^٥

In Al-Qamoos al-Wafi, it refers to Nikhil

"النخل والنخيل النخلة؛ شجرة من الفصيلة النخيلة كثيرة في البلاد العرب ولا سيما الحجاز ولعراق ومصر ويزرع لثمرة المعروف بالبلح والتمر، والزرينة (ج) نخل (ج) نخيل."^٦

Imam Raghīb Isfahani, al-Mufardat fi Gharib al-Qur'an

"النَّخْلُ معروف، وقد يُستعمل في الواحد والجمع. قال تعالى كَأَنَّهُمْ أَعْجَازُ نَخْلٍ مُنْقَعِرٍ وجمعه نَخِيلٌ، قال وَمِنْ ثَمَرَاتِ النَّخِيلِ وَالنَّخْلِ نَخْلٌ دَقِيقٌ بِالنُّخْلِ، وَانْتَخَلْتُ الشَّيْءَ انْتَقَيْتُهُ فَأَخَذْتُ خِيَارَهُ."^٧

Urdu dictionary on historical principle; The palm has been described as follows.

"The date palm is a desert tree with a long, straight, and Slight, Italy curved trunk. There is a canopy at the top, which has branches. Some of them are facing upwards and some are facing downwards. Its fruit is under the branches which is very sweet."⁸

According to the Oxford Advanced Learner Dictionary

"Date fruit, a sweet sickly brown that great tree called a date palm common in Africa and west Asia."⁹

"The date is one-seeded fruit or berry usually oblong but varying in shape and size. Color quality and consistency of flesh according to the condition."¹⁰ The Hutchison Encyclopedia Dictionary "Date; date oblong brown sweet edible fruit of palm tree."¹¹

Dates and Quran

Dates in the Holy Quran are mentioned twenty-two times in different surahs, which shows their importance and status. It is mentioned in the fruits of both worlds. The Arabs use dates a lot. It is used as food and medicine.

"أَيُّودٌ أَحَدُكُمْ أَنْ تَكُونَ لَهُ جَنَّةٌ مِنْ نَخِيلٍ وَأَعْنَابٍ بِجَرِيِّ مِنْ تَحْتِهَا الْأَنْهَارُ لَهُ فِيهَا مِنْ كُلِّ الثَّمَرَاتِ وَأَصَابَهُ الْكِبَرُ وَلَهُ ذُرِّيَّةٌ ضُعَفَاءُ فَأَصَابَهَا إِعْصَارٌ فِيهِ نَارٌ فَاحْتَرَقَتْ كَذَلِكَ يُبَيِّنُ اللَّهُ لَكُمْ الْآيَاتِ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَتَفَكَّرُونَ."^{١٢}

"Would any of you want s to have a garden full of dates? Full of dates and grapes with rivers flowing beneath it, where he might find every sort of fruit, and then, when he reaches old ages and his children become too frail to support themselves a whirlwind wind with fire comes and burns all down for you to r reflect Allah makes the signs obvious to you in this manner."

" يُبَيِّنُ لَكُمْ بِهِ الزَّرْعَ وَالزَّيْتُونَ وَالنَّخِيلَ وَالْأَعْنَابَ وَمِنْ كُلِّ الثَّمَرَاتِ إِنَّ فِي ذَلِكَ لَآيَةً لِقَوْمٍ يَتَفَكَّرُونَ."^{١٣}

God produces crops and many kinds of fruits, including olives, dates, and Graphs certainly have a message for those who think.

In this verse of the Quran, dates have been mentioned as a blessed fruit Quran has mentioned in Surah Maryam, When Hazrat Maryam was worried about her future, baby, and blame which was blamed by the people. In a time of worry, she separated herself.

"فَأَجَاءَهَا الْمَخَاضُ إِلَى جِذْعِ النَّخْلَةِ قَالَتْ يَا لَيْتَنِي مِتُّ قَبْلَ هَذَا وَكُنْتُ نَسِيًّا مَنْسِيًّا."^{١٤}

"When she fell into labor pains, she went under the palm tree—and said Oh My God. Sorry that I had died before this time everything about me had been forgotten"

"وَالْأَرْضَ وَضَعَهَا لِلْأَنَامِ فِيهَا فَاكِهَةٌ وَالنَّخْلُ ذَاتُ الْأَكْمَامِ."^{١٥}

"And the land made for sleeping. In it, there are fruits and palm trees with sheaths"

Allah has mentioned plants but some fruits are mentioned by name due to their impatience, all these trees that are mentioned in the Quran and Hadith are blessed

"فَأَنْشَأْنَا لَكُمْ بِهِ جَنَّاتٍ مِنْ نَجِيلٍ وَأَعْنَابٍ لَكُمْ فِيهَا فَوَاكِهُ كَثِيرَةٌ وَمِنْهَا تَأْكُلُونَ"^{١٦}

"We created for you gardens of palm trees and grapevines for you therein are abundant fruits and from them, you may eat"

Dates and Hadiths of the Prophet

Dates have been mentioned in Sahih Bukhari under different topics two hundred hadiths are reported mentioning their medicinal and diet importance in the beginning it was used as a bed and Quranic Ayat was written on its leaves. In Sahih Muslim, there are 100 Hadiths on dates that describe its benefits as a medicine and diet.¹⁷

"عَنْ مُجَاهِدٍ، قَالَ سَمِعْتُ ابْنَ عُمَرَ، عَنِ النَّبِيِّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ قَالَ إِنَّ مِنَ الشَّجَرِ شَجَرَةً، تَكُونُ

مِثْلَ الْمُسْلِمِ، وَهِيَ النَّخْلَةُ."^{١٨}

"This is mentioned by Hazrat Mujahd he says that I have heard from Ibin E Umar and he has taken it from the Holy prophet (May God peace and blessing upon him) that there is a tree in the world of tree named dates tree likewise Muslim"

"عَنْ أَبِي هُرَيْرَةَ، أَنَّ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ كَانَ إِذَا أَتَى بِأَوَّلِ التَّمْرَةِ قَالَ اللَّهُمَّ بَارِكْ لَنَا فِي

مَدِينَتِنَا، وَفِي نَمَارِنَا، وَفِي مُدِّنَا، وَفِي صَاعِنَا، بَرَكَةً مَعَ بَرَكَةٍ، ثُمَّ يُنَاوِلُهُ أَصْغَرَ مَنْ بَحْضَرْتِهِ مِنَ الْوِلْدَانِ."^{١٩}

"Narrated by Hazrat Abu Harara (RA) when the Messenger of God, may God peace be upon him said "O God bless for us this city and in our fruits, when was brought the first fruit of any season gives this fruit first to the youngest who was present that time"

"مَنْ أَكَلَ سَبْعَ تَمْرَاتٍ مِمَّا بَيْنَ لَابَتَيْهَا حِينَ يُصْبِحُ، لَمْ يَضُرَّهُ سُمٌّ حَتَّى يُمْسِيَ."^{٢٠}

"When in the morning someone eats seven dates of Madina no poison can harm him until the evening"

"أَنَّسَ بْنَ مَالِكٍ يُقُولُ كَانَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ يُفْطِرُ عَلَى رُطَبَاتٍ قَبْلَ أَنْ يُصَلِّيَ، فَإِنْ لَمْ تَكُنْ رُطَبَاتٌ، فَعَلَى تَمْرَاتٍ، فَإِنْ لَمْ تَكُنْ حَسَا حَسَوَاتٍ مِنْ مَاءٍ." ٢١

"This is narrated by Hazrat Anus bin Malak He said: That the Prophet of God (May God' peace and blessing be upon him) Eats wet dates at the breaking time of the fast before he prayed if there are no wet dates then use to ordinary dates, in case of nothing use to sips of water"

"عَنْ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ بْنِ جَعْفَرِ بْنِ أَبِي طَالِبٍ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُمَا، قَالَ رَأَيْتُ النَّبِيَّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ يَأْكُلُ الرُّطَبَ بِالِقِتَاءِ." ٢٢

"Abdul Aziz bin Abdullah told us, he says I Ibrahim bin Saad told me, on the authority of his father, on the authority of Abdullah Ja'far bin Abi Talib God bin Abi Talib may God be pleased with him, said I saw Prophet (may God peace be upon him) eating fresh dates with cucumbers"

"قَالَ تَصَيَّفْتُ أَبَا هُرَيْرَةَ، سَبْعًا، فَكَانَ هُوَ وَامْرَأَتُهُ وَخَادِمُهُ يَغْتَقِبُونَ اللَّيْلَ أَثْلَاثًا يُصَلِّي هَذَا، ثُمَّ يُوقِظُ هَذَا، وَسَمِعْتُهُ يَقُولُ فَسَمَّ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ بَيْنَ أَصْحَابِهِ تَمْرًا، فَأَصَابَنِي سَبْعُ تَمْرَاتٍ، إِحْدَاهُنَّ حَشَفَةٌ." ٢٣

"He said: I hosted Abu Hurairah for seven days, and he, his wife, and his servant used to watch three people at night. This man would pray, then he would wake this man up, and I heard He says: The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, divided dates among his companions, and seven dates came to me, one of them a Hashfa"

" حَدَّثَنِي مُجَاهِدٌ، عَنْ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ بْنِ عُمَرَ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُمَا قَالَ: «بَيْنَمَا نَحْنُ عِنْدَ النَّبِيِّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ جُلُوسٌ إِذَا أَبِي بِجُمَارِ نَخْلَةٍ، فَقَالَ النَّبِيُّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ: إِنَّ مِنَ الشَّجَرِ لَمَا بَرَكَتُهُ كَبَرَكَةِ الْمُسْلِمِ، فَظَنَنْتُ أَنَّهُ يَعْنِي النَّخْلَةَ، فَأَرَدْتُ أَنْ أَقُولَ هِيَ النَّخْلَةُ يَا رَسُولَ اللَّهِ، ثُمَّ التَّفْتُ، فَإِذَا أَنَا عَاشِرٌ عَشْرَةَ أَنَا أَخَذْتُهُمْ، فَسَكَتُ، فَقَالَ النَّبِيُّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ: هِيَ النَّخْلَةُ." ٢٤

"Umar bin Hafs bin Ghayath told us: My father told us: Al-A`Amash told us He said: Mujahid told me on the authority of Abdullah bin Omar, may God be pleased with him About them, he said: While we were sitting with the Prophet, may God prayers and peace be upon him, then a bunch of dates was presented in front Hazrat Muhammad (peace and blessing of Allah be upon him) The Prophet of Allah,(May God prayer and bless be upon him) there is tree having bless in it likewise a Muslim. then I thought about it, maybe it was the dates tree I decided to reply it's the dates tree of the Messenger of God but kept silent

because I was the tenth of ten youngest in them. Then the Holy Prophet (May God's peace be upon him) replied that it was a date tree"
" أَخْبَرَنَا عَامِرُ بْنُ سَعْدٍ، عَنْ أَبِيهِ، قَالَ قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ مَنْ تَصَبَّحَ كُلَّ يَوْمٍ سَبْعَ تَمْرَاتٍ عَجْوَةً، لَمْ يَضُرَّهُ فِي ذَلِكَ الْيَوْمِ سُمْ وَلَا سِحْرٌ. " ٢٥

"Jumah bin Abdullah told us, Marwan told us, Hashim bin Hashim told us, Amer bin Saad told us, on the authority of his father, he said: The Messenger of God said: May God's prayers and peace be upon him: Whoever eats seven dates every morning, no poison or magic will harm him on that day"

"رَأَيْتُ النَّبِيَّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ أَخَذَ كِسْرَةً مِنْ حُبْزِ شَعِيرٍ فَوَضَعَ عَلَيْهَا تَمْرَةً، وَقَالَ هَذِهِ إِدَامٌ هَذِهِ. " ٢٦

"The above-mentioned Hadith has been mentioned by Harum bn Abdullah, Muhammad bin Abi Yahya, Yusuf bin Abdullah says I saw the Prophet of Allah (may God peace be upon him Allah) took a piece of barley bread and put a date on it and said this is a curry of it"

"On the authority of Anas bin Malik: A delegation of Abdul Qais from the people of Hijr came to the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, and said: The best of your dates, Al-Barani, it cures the disease and there is no disease in it.²⁷"

"عَنْ عَائِشَةَ رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهَا، قَالَتْ قَالَ النَّبِيُّ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ بَيْتٌ لَا تَمْرٌ فِيهِ، جِيَاعٌ أَهْلُهُ. " ٢٨

"Reported on the authority of Hazrat Aisha, may God be pleased with her, she said: That, The Prophet of God, may God's prayers and peace be him, said: If the house is without a palm tree, The residents of this are hungry"

" كَانَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ يَأْكُلُ الْبَطِيخَ بِالرُّطْبِ فَيَقُولُ نَكْسِرُ حَرَّ هَذَا بِرَدِّ هَذَا، وَبِرَدِّ هَذَا بِحَرِّ هَذَا " ٢٩

"The Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, used to eat watermelon with dates, and he would say: We break this's heat with the cold of this, and we break this's cold with this's heat."

Dates have been mentioned many times in the Hadith under different topics. Only in Bukhari Sharif, dates have been mentioned two hundred and fourteen times.

Temperament of date

"وَهُوَ حَارٌّ فِي الثَّانِيَةِ، وَهَلْ هُوَ رَطْبٌ فِي الْأُولَى، أَوْ يَابِسٌ فِيهَا؟ عَلَى قَوْلَيْنِ. " ٣٠

"Imam Dahbi has mentioned it as hot dried; it is curative in impotency.³¹

Chemical constituents of dates

NUTRITIONAL AND MEDICINAL IMPORTANCE OF DATES IN THE LIGHT OF QURAN, HADITH, AND MEDICAL SCIENCE

Dates are the main source of carbohydrates, fiber, minerals, and several essential vitamins, magnesium, phosphorus, potassium, and vitamin B6 including low cholesterol and fat levels making them a healthy food choice due to their high carbohydrate and fiber content most effective to provide sustained energy and improved digestion.

Dates –Nutritional Facts per 100g

Nutrients mg percentage

Folate	15ug	4%
Niacin	1.610mg	10%
Pantothenic acid	0.805mg	16%
Paridocaine	0.249mg	19%
Riboflavin	0.060m	4.5%
Thiamin	0.050mg	4%
Vitamin A	149iu	5%
Vitamin C	0mg	0%
itamin K	2.7ug	2%
Sodium	1mg	0%
Potassium	696mg	16%
Calcium	64mg	6.5%
Copper	0.362mg	40%
Iron	0.90mg	11%
Magnesium	54mg	13%
Manganese	0.296mg	13%
Phosphorus	62mg	9%
Zinc	0.44mg	4%

32

Dates are well known in richness of Koli calories there is a sufficient quantity of carbohydrates in dried dates weight is 73% which are basically Glucose90% fructose, and sucrose.³³

Medicinal Benefits of Dates

Medical science and nutrition have brought the importance of dates as a medicine to the level of evidence. Calcium present in dates plays an important role in the strength and maturity of bones and it also contains phosphorus. From which the real elements of the brain are formed. It also protects the nerves from weakness and fatigue and increases eyesight. It also contains potassium, while the lack of potassium in the body is considered to be the real cause of stomach ulcers, and its existence is very valuable for the muscles and body tissue. Dates prevent cancer because the data provided in this regard indicate that areas, where dates are eaten more often, have a lower incidence of cancer. Bedouins and desert dwellers of Arabs, whose lives are spent in poverty and hunger, have never suffered from cancer due to eating dates. The reason for this is that magnesium is present in dates.

There is a lot of sugar in dates and it is a more correct and better type of sugar, even people suffering from diabetes can use it comfortably on some occasions. Scientists have identified thirteen types of vital substances and five types of antioxidants in dates, which shows that it is a very valuable and rich food.

"Nourishing and strength giving, beneficial in plethora flatulence cough, cold, asthma, clearing, phlegm, hysteria, blood purifier thirst, hunger, fever, cystitis, gonorrhea, edema, liver, and abdominal troubles. Cures. The diseases caused by milk after eating Dates give agility and strength. Boiled water with Hula (fenugreek) and dates is a good tonic Water soaked in Dates Overnight and taken with honey is beneficial in cases of enlarged liver and spleen. Energy, 277 Kcal \ 100g."³⁴

It is benefice in abdomen diseases, stomach, liver, intestinal diseases, acidity, and alkaline phosphate. Hepatoprotective activity Prevent dimethoate-induced hepatotoxicity decrease hepatic markers (ALT, AST, alkaline phosphatase, GGT, and LDH), and decrease vacuolization, necrosis, congestion, inflammation, and enlargement of sinusoids. Has a protective effect against CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity.³⁵ Different parts of the palm are used for medical treatment and their medicinal use is as follows

Fruit – sweet, cooling, tonic, fattening, aphrodisiac, useful in leprosy, thirst, asthma, bronchitis, Fatigue, tuberculosis, abdominal complaints, fever, vomiting, loss of consciousness

Leaf – Aphrodisiac and good for the liver.

Flowers – Bitter, purgative, expectorant, liver tonic, fever and blood complaints

Seeds – applied to wounds, sores, and inflammations. It is impure, expectorant, laxative, nutritive, and recommended in case of asthma, and gonorrhea.

Gum - useful remedy in diarrhea and genitourinary disease.³⁶

Observations of physicians on dates

Doctors have written about dates, dates have a unique and complete diet, all nutrients are found in it in abundance, Maulana Haroon Muawiya writes about it like this. carotene) -inflammatory activity Increases plasma antioxidant (Vitamin C, E, A, B-Anti³⁷ levels and decreases lipid peroxides. Reduce swelling, ESR, and plasma fibrinogen.³⁸ Antihyperlipidemic activity Reduces plasma triglycerides, total and LDL cholesterol ³⁹ In the case of diseases caused by phlegm and cold, eating dates is useful. It reduces the weakness of the brain whose memory is weak. It strengthens the kidneys. It relieves respiratory distress. Dates are very useful for asthma patients. Using dates in coughs, fevers and peaches relieves constipation. It is a diuretic and increases energy. Action on ⁴⁰ gastrointestinal tract Increase gastrointestinal transit time reduces ethanol-induced gastric ulceration",⁴¹

Regarding dates, Dr. Ganesh Narayan has described his observations as follows. Dates are beneficial in dry cough and asthma, and dissolve to inflammation Dates are useful for TB patients, diabetes and other diseases in which patients desire sweet food while sweet foods are harmful to them can take dates palm ⁴²"

NUTRITIONAL AND MEDICINAL IMPORTANCE OF DATES IN THE LIGHT OF QURAN, HADITH, AND MEDICAL SCIENCE

Improves the kidneys and their functions reduces the level of creatinine, improves the urinary system, and cures its related disorders. Date fruits are high in calories and contain a variety of essential nutrients such as antioxidants, minerals, carbohydrates, proteins, and fiber.⁴³

Nephroprotective activity Prevents gentamicin-induced renal damage and reduces Creatinine and urea levels⁴⁴ Anticancer activity Regression of Sarcoma-180 tumor in mice⁴⁵ Immunostimulant activity Enhance both cell-mediated and humoral immunity.⁴⁶ Increases the number of sex hormones, testosterone, LH, FSH, estrogen, and sperm Gonadotropic activity Increase FSH, LH, testosterone, and estrogen—increase spermatogenesis, sperm count, and growth.⁴⁷

A study conducted at King Fahd Civil Hospital Tabuk included 89 pregnant women. 26 were fed only fresh dates while 32 were given 250 ml of water after fresh dates. 31 was left alone. It was observed that the first and third stages of labor were established quickly and easily in those fed fresh dates (especially those that were watered). Likewise, a positive effect on the child's health was also seen. Therefore, the women who were given dates did not have complications related to childbirth, such as irregular heartbeat, etc. in their children.⁴⁸

Dates do not increase the diabetic rate in a patient due to the chemical substance invertase which converts its sugar into fructose. Fructose has such characteristics that control raising the value of sugar⁴⁹ Several studies have found that as dates mature, their chemical makeup and overall composition change significantly. The amount of reduced sugar in the dates increases, while the levels of fiber, minerals, and vitamins gradually decrease.

Prevention about dates

There are some precautions about dates that are mentioned in Hadith books and other Islamic literature and observation of *Muhaddithen*, Researchers, and medical science views, all going parallel to each other.

Pam dates have many medicinal benefits on mucus cold temperamental bodies power tonic and are useful in all the diseases in this temperament. As narrated by Hazrat Jabar bin Abdullah (RA) Hazrat Muhammad (peace be upon him) forbade us to eat dates with raisins.

"أَنَّهُ نَهَى أَنْ يُنْبَدَ الرَّيْبُ وَالْتَّمْرُ جَمِيعًا. وَنَهَى أَنْ يُنْبَدَ الْبُسْرُ وَالرُّطْبُ جَمِيعًا."⁵⁰

The same statement in Tirmizi Al Nasai and (Hadith's book) reported by Abdullah bin Qatada (RA) Hazrat Ayesha and Hazrat Umah Salma (RA) stated that the Prophet of Allah Hazrat Muhammad (may God peace be upon him) said do not eat old and unrapid dates at once Imam. Abin e Qayyum reported a hadith without authority that the prophet of God said do not eat Figs and dates at once.⁵¹

Umah Manzar (RA) says that Hazrat Muhammad ﷺ came into our house, and Hazrat Ali (RA) was also with him. The bunches of dates were hanging in our house at that time. Hazrat Ali (RA) Messenger of Allah started to eat Allah's Messenger said to Ali (RA) O Ali "Enough you have recently recovered Hazrat Ali (RA) stopped eating while the Prophet ate the dates

then I prepared beetroot and barley Put it in front of both Prophet of Allah said O Ali take it. It is beneficial for you.⁵² Catalase plays a significant role in controlling reactive oxygen species, particularly hydrogen peroxide. It is an important anti-oxidative enzyme and is particularly effective in managing the levels of hydrogen peroxide in the body.⁵³ Hazrat Sohaib (RA) says that he was in a meeting with the Prophet of Allah and was eating dates these days and was suffering from conjunctivitis The Prophet (May God's peace be upon him) of God said you are eating dates while you are suffering from conjunctivitis.⁵⁴

Dates are not beneficial for those patients who are suffering from diseases caused by hot-dried temperament, it may cause jaundice, enlargement of the liver, hypertrophy, and Anemia. Dysentery and edema etc.

Do not take two or more things in the same temperament at once. A Diet Study of Hazrat Muhammad ﷺ shows he did not collect any two drinking or eating things of the same temperament likewise Hazrat Muhammad (Peace be upon him) took dates in his food and then took cucumber to reduce the hotness of dates

Results

The gathered information improved that. Dates are a combination of several medicines, which are anti-hyperlipidemic, anti-hydrolipidic, anti-cancer, anti-cancer, gastro-protective, hepato-protective, hepato-protective, and nephron-protective. It has a diverse chemical composition along with mineral content in which vitamins (A, B1, B2, B3, B6, B9, and C) are found. Which is important for carbohydrates, fat, protein, and metabolism, and regulates the immune system. It contains magnesium, copper, iron, selenium, potassium, phosphorus, and calcium, which play an important role in the digestive system. Dates are very useful in high blood pressure, and intestinal cancer, cure gastro and constipation, and in all diseases caused by cold and dry mood, no food is better than dates because of its no harmful effects. in comparison, other drugs have side effects. Dates are free from side effects and have good results in heart disorders. It boosts the immune system effectively. Every kind of date has its own temperament and curative value. Dates are part of your diet on a daily basis which are cheap It also plays an important role in physical development. Its importance is clearly described in the Qur'an and Hadith, which have been confirmed by modern research. More research is needed on its various components, which within the passage of time. Will continue

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NUTRITIONAL AND MEDICINAL IMPORTANCE OF DATES IN THE LIGHT OF QURAN, HADITH, AND MEDICAL SCIENC

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